

Important terms of contracts on the provision of charitable assistance to mahalla citizens' assemblies by individuals and legal entities

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Abstract. This article comprehensively analyzes the legal nature, social significance and important terms of contracts on the provision of charitable assistance to mahalla citizens' assemblies by individuals and legal entities. The study covers the civil-legal foundations of the charity contract, the important, usual and accidental terms of the contract theoretically and practically.

The article also analyzes the subject of the contract, the purposeful use of charitable property, accounting and control mechanisms, the consequences of violating the terms, the procedure for changing the purpose, and the issues of the legal balance between the freedom of the contract and the social purpose.

Basic concepts. Mahalla citizens' assembly, charity agreement, charity, gift agreement, important conditions, freedom of contract, public benefit purpose, accountability, financial control, legal balance, civil society, targeted use.

Before analyzing the important conditions of agreements on charitable assistance to mahalla citizens' assemblies by individuals and legal entities, it is necessary to explain the relevance, importance and necessity of this agreement.

The relevance of agreements on charitable assistance to mahalla citizens' assemblies by individuals and legal entities is primarily related to the role of the mahalla institution in society and its constitutional status. Citizens' self-government bodies are important in the socio-economic life of the population, they are directly involved in meeting the daily needs of the population, supporting the strata in need of social protection, and implementing various cultural and educational projects. Charitable assistance is one of the important sources that strengthens the financial and material foundations of the mahalla and replenishes the capabilities of the state budget. The charitable institutions provided for in Article 511 of the Civil Code and the financial basis established in Article 27 of the Law "On Self-Government Bodies of Citizens" further enhance the importance of patronage and charity in the fully effective functioning of the mahalla.

Today, since the mahalla system is of particular importance not only in state policy, but also in strengthening civil society institutions, the relevance of legally regulating charitable relations through contracts is increasing. Because ensuring transparency in mahalla activities, targeted use of funds, and increasing the trust of donors are among the important criteria in a modern democratic society. Therefore, charitable contracts concluded with individuals and legal entities are of great importance not only as a legal

basis, but also as an important tool of practical and social significance.

The importance of providing charitable assistance to the mahalla citizens' assembly by individuals and legal entities on a contractual basis is determined, first of all, by ensuring legal guarantees. According to the general rules of the Civil Code, a contract clearly defines the rights and obligations of the parties and guarantees the stability of relations. Thus, through charity contracts, the targeted allocation of funds or material assets provided by the donor and their effective use are ensured. Secondly, through a contract, charitable relations are made transparent and accountable. The donor has the right to control the spending of the donation, and the mahalla assumes the obligation to maintain and submit its report. This strengthens the trust of donors and increases the reputation of the mahalla in the eyes of the general public. Thirdly, the importance of the contract is manifested in the socio-economic development of the mahalla and improving the quality of life of the population. For example, charitable funds can be used to provide material assistance to low-income families, support projects in the fields of education and healthcare, and carry out infrastructure development. Finally, the importance of contracts is also clearly visible in the development of civil society. Because a contract, as a legal basis, raises the legal awareness of the mahalla and citizens and increases their legal culture. Thus, charity contracts not only ensure the financial stability of the mahalla, but are also an important mechanism for building a legal democratic state. The need for individuals and legal entities to provide charitable assistance to the mahalla citizens' assembly on a contractual basis is explained by a number of legal, economic and social factors. First of all, this need is associated with the need to ensure the financial independence of the activities of citizens' self-government bodies. The state budget cannot fully cover the needs of all mahallas, therefore, patronage and charity become one of the main financial sources of the mahalla. This must be legally strengthened through contracts. Secondly, the need is associated with the principles of accountability and transparency. If a charity contract is not concluded, the spending of charitable funds may remain unclear and uncontrolled. The contract guarantees the targeted spending of funds and their registration. Thirdly, the need for a contract is also related to protecting the interests of the donor. According to Article 511 of the Civil Code, in cases where the stated purpose is violated, the donor has the right to terminate the contract and demand the return of the donation. This is an important legal guarantee for the donor. Fourthly, the need is aimed at effectively fulfilling the social tasks of the mahalla. Because through charity contracts, the mahalla's tasks of social protection of the population, implementation of cultural and educational activities, development of infrastructure and improvement of the living standards of the population are ensured. Thus, the need for contracts is explained by ensuring the stability of legal relations, targeted and effective spending of funds, protection of the interests of donors and ensuring the socio-economic stability of the mahalla.

Thus, it can be concluded that the need and importance of contractual relations related to donations made by individuals and legal entities to the mahalla citizens' assembly are urgent.

Since it is necessary to talk about the essential terms of contracts on the provision of charitable assistance to mahalla citizen assemblies by individuals and legal entities, it is appropriate to analyze their essential terms in the context of the contracts under Article 364 of the Civil Code. According to I.B. Zokirov, the terms (clauses) of the contract are divided into essential, usual and incidental terms.

The terms on the subject of the contract are those that are considered essential or necessary for such contracts in the legislation, as well as all terms that must be agreed upon at the request of one of the parties. Specific essential terms for some contracts are determined by law [1]. Similar opinions are expressed by Z.I. Yuldashev. In his opinion, in the process of concluding a contract, the terms that are considered essential for this type of contract should be agreed upon. Essential terms can be divided into three categories:

- 1) conditions on the subject of the contract;
- 2) conditions that are considered essential or necessary for such types of contracts in the legislation;
- 3) all conditions that must be agreed upon at the request of one of the parties are also considered essential conditions [2].

The views of I.B. Zokirov and Z.I. Yuldashev are generally consistent in determining the essential conditions in the content of the contract, and both of the views cited take into account the essence of Article 364 of the Criminal Code.

Thus, the views of the two scholars are complementary: I.B. Zokirov gives a theoretical classification of conditions, while Z.I. Yuldashev emphasizes the need to determine them in practice according to the characteristics of the type of contract. The form and procedure of charity (one-time, step-by-step, conditional or unconditional) must be agreed upon. I.B. Zokirov's theoretically based classification and J.I. Yuldashev's approach to practice, when used together, provide a harmonious solution to the theory and practice of contract law.

As for the usual terms of the contract, they are terms that relate to issues that have already been regulated by dispositive norms in the legislation. They do not have to be separately specified in the contract, since they operate "by themselves". If the parties wish, they can deviate from the general rule in the legislation and establish another rule, but if the contract is silent on this, the dispositive norm of the law applies. For example, in a property lease agreement, minor (current) repairs of the property may or may not be specified as a condition, since this condition is indicated in the legislation (of a dispositive nature). Incidental terms are terms that the parties mutually determine on issues that are not regulated by the legislation and for which there is no clear rule in the

general norms. Their existence follows from the principle of freedom of contract. If this condition is not specified in the contract, it is considered completely absent and the law does not automatically supplement it.

It should be noted that the contract may provide for the determination of some of its terms by standard terms developed for the relevant type of contract. In cases where the contract does not refer to standard terms, such standard terms are applied to the relations of the parties as business practices (Article 359 of the Civil Code).

The subject of the contract is understood as the object to which the rights and obligations of the parties are directed and the purpose of concluding the contract. Usually, the subject of the contract can be interpreted as objects of civil rights. The objects of civil rights include things, including money and securities, other items, property, including property rights, works and services, inventions, industrial designs, works of science, literature, art and other results of intellectual activity, as well as personal non-property rights and other tangible and intangible assets. In this case, tangible and intangible benefits that are objects of civil law are considered as the subject of the contract. For example, if movable and immovable property are the subject of purchase and sale, gift, rent, lease agreements, then the life and health of a citizen can be the subject of an insurance contract.

When concluding any contract, its subject must first be agreed upon, and if the contract is concluded in writing, this condition must be reflected in the text of the contract. When determining the subject of the contract, the parties must clearly express it, based on the purpose and nature of each contract. For example, in a real estate donation contract, the name, location and type of real estate that is the subject of the contract are clearly expressed on the basis of relevant cadastral documents. The next category of essential conditions includes conditions that are considered important or necessary in the legislation for this type of contract. For certain types of contracts, essential conditions are separately indicated in the legislation.

Any condition that must be agreed upon at the request of one of the parties is recognized as an essential condition. Since the contract is a document expressing the will of the parties, it is necessary to agree on the circumstances that each party considers necessary. Such a condition, regardless of its significance and content for the contract, must be reflected in the contract as an essential condition. For example, in a product delivery contract, the buyer may require the seller to specify the exact day of the week and at what time of day the product will be delivered and agree on this with the seller. In this case, such a condition becomes the main condition of the product delivery contract. The absence of a condition that is essential for the relevant contract in the text of the contract means that the contract has not been concluded. A contract in which an essential condition is not expressed may be declared invalid by the court at the request of an interested party. A contract that does not express essential conditions is considered invalid as a transaction whose content does not comply with the requirements of the

legislation (Article 116 of the Civil Code). The reflection of circumstances that are recognized as usual terms of the contract does not create a special need for the contract to reflect. The fact that such conditions are stipulated in the legislation or can be determined even after the conclusion of the contract does not entail any specific legal consequences if they are not included in the contract. For example, the method of delivery of the product, the place of performance of the obligation, etc. In particular, in a contract for home renovation, the place of performance of the obligation is not required to be included in the contract, and this is understood from the essence of the obligation and is carried out at the location of the house, or the place of performance of the obligation can be determined based on the requirements of Article 246 of the Civil Code.

Based on these analyses, it is considered expedient to analyze the specific features of charitable donation contracts concluded by individuals and legal entities to the mahalla citizens' assembly and the important terms of this contract.

The rules on charitable donations are established in Article 511 of the Civil Code, which states that charitable donations are a gift of a thing or right for public benefit. Charity can be carried out in the interests of citizens, educational, scientific and medical institutions, museums, foundations.

A charity contract is one of the special types of a gift contract. Its legal form is still controversial and relevant in modern conditions. Because participants in civil transactions often formalize a sale-purchase contract in the form of a gift contract or a charity contract in order to avoid paying mandatory payments. This work reveals the essence of a charity contract, examines some of its important elements and features. Given the increasing importance of a charity contract, the controversial aspect of this issue is of urgent importance and is of great importance both theoretically and practically [3].

It should be noted that the gift contract itself is one of the oldest contracts and is included in the list of fiduciary contracts. Because usually its parties are relatives, and they made it through the gift in order to increase the property of the individual and to be useful to him (expecting to have a warm attitude towards the donor). Thus, there is a correlation between these goals.

In the donation contract, the subjects may be not only relatives, but also the following:

- citizens;
- medical and educational institutions;
- social service organizations;
- charitable and scientific organizations;
- foundations, cultural organizations;
- public associations and religious organizations [4].

Compared to a gift contract, it has a broader subject: things, rights, and exemption from obligations, while a donation contract does not provide for exemption from obligations

at all. According to D.R. Sultanova and A.A. Sigacheva, if exemption from obligations were possible, this would make it impossible to use the gift for its intended purpose [5]. According to K.B. Novikov, there are certain features inherent in a donation contract, which are as follows:

- relatively narrow subject: things or rights; unlike a gift contract, exemption from debt is not included in it;
- exclusion of commercial organizations from the composition of subjects, that is, they do not participate as donees (recipients of charity);
- the goal is clearly defined - a public benefit goal[6].

Scientists - D.R. Sultanova, A.A. Sigacheva and K.B. Novikov - emphasize that the charity contract has its own features, independent of the gift contract. Their opinion is logically justified: indeed, the main goal of charity is a public benefit direction, which distinguishes its legal nature from a simple gift. Therefore, the absence of the possibility of exemption from obligations or the exclusion of commercial organizations as recipients follows from the socially oriented nature of the contract. However, the unilateral acceptance of this point of view is incomplete. For example, the absolute exclusion of exemption from obligations narrows the scope of the principle of freedom of contract. Also, the participation of commercial organizations as beneficiaries is not always undesirable, since in some cases socially significant projects can be implemented through them. Thus, although the distinctions noted by these scholars are theoretically correct, in practice the freedom of contract and the harmony of the social goal should be preserved. It would be more correct to distinguish a charity contract not with absolute restrictions, but with a common-interest goal and transparent control. I.A. Minakhina defines charity as follows: “goals related to satisfying the material and spiritual needs of citizens, the development of science, culture, education” [7], that is, goals in the form of supporting or contributing to the development of humanistic values in society. The implementation of a common-interest goal raises the question of the possibility of anonymous charity. Since the composition of subjects is quite wide, including religious associations, and the texts of major religions indicate that anonymous charity is encouraged. In comparison with European practice, we can cite the opinion of William A. Drennan. According to him, in the USA, it is not practical to make large donations completely anonymously. Since in some cases the donor may have vested interests, for example, to avoid closing accounts in case of debt (bankruptcy). Anonymity is also undesirable, since the donor will need to obtain the appropriate supporting documents to receive tax benefits [8].

A charity contract includes several main elements. In particular, the parties to this contract are the donor (donor) and the donee (recipient), and the subject of the contract is property. Property is transferred to the donee free of charge for public benefit purposes on the basis of ownership. As for the form of the contract, a written form is mandatory in the following cases: if real estate is being transferred; if a promise to

donate in the future is being made; if the charity contract is concluded by a legal entity and the value of the property exceeds three thousand rubles.

A donation contract can be both real and consensual, but the donation is considered to have been made from the moment the funds are transferred to the account or the property is reflected in the balance sheet of the donee, or from the moment documents confirming the transfer of the right of claim are submitted [9]

One of the evidences that the charity contract undoubtedly belongs to the gift contract is that Article 511 of the Civil Code (on charity) is located in Chapter 32 of the Civil Code, which is called "Gift". Also, both charity and gift are bilateral agreements, and their composition of subjects is almost identical. A charity contract is concluded on the same basis and has many features characteristic of a gift contract. However, there are some specific features that allow us to consider charity as an independent element. The most important of them is that charity is carried out only for public benefit purposes. In a typical gift contract, it is not important for the donor how and when the donee will use it. In a charity contract, the goals are determined in advance, and this goal is the main motive for concluding the contract. Currently, there are several main points of view in scientific literature on this matter. For example, A.B. According to Borisov, what distinguishes a gift from a charity is the designated purpose of the gift, which must be used in a specific direction, and if there is no such condition, the transfer of property for free is considered a simple gift [10]. M.F. Kazantsev believes that this purpose serves as a condition limiting the right of the donee to property [11].

I.A. Minakhina's definition of charity as material and spiritual goals aimed at the development of humanistic values in society reveals the socially oriented nature of charity. Her opinion has a logical basis: charity, unlike a simple gift, should serve not individual interests, but general social benefits. From this point of view, she puts the criterion of purpose in the legal nature of charity in the first place.

A.B. Borisov emphasizes that the most important feature of a gift is the obligation to use it for the intended purpose. His opinion is justified, since the transfer of property without a specific purpose is considered a simple gift. However, this approach can in some cases limit the freedom of contract: if the donor does not specify the purpose, but the social direction is clear, assessing it as a simple gift can lead to a contradictory situation.

M.F. Kazantsev sees the intended purpose as a circumstance that limits the donee's right to property. This idea can be supported from the point of view of social justice, since the redirection of donated property to another purpose violates the donor's will. However, this restriction should not unduly reduce the donee's property rights: especially in cases where the situation has changed and the intended purpose cannot be realized, the possibility of changing the purpose with the consent of the court or the donor must be preserved.

Thus, a donation contract, as a separate type of a gift contract, occupies an important

place in legal theory and practice. Its main feature is its orientation towards public benefit goals, which is precisely what distinguishes it from a simple gift. If in a gift contract the further fate of the property is not important for the donor, then in a donation contract the use of the property for the intended purpose is a condition, which determines its legal nature. Although the current legislation contains norms for donation contracts, they are not sufficiently perfect from a practical point of view. Because the rights of the donee are not always fully protected, the balance between freedom of contract and public benefit is a subject of constant debate. Therefore, it is necessary to further modernize and clarify the institution of this contract in the legislation. Research shows that although a donation contract is within the framework of a gift contract, there are signs indicating that it has an independent legal status. The most important of them is the social predetermination of the fate of property and the obligation of the donee to use the property for its intended purpose.

Thus, the donation contract should be recognized as an independent institution within the framework of the gift contract. Improving its legal form should be carried out in such directions as:

- more clearly defining the concept of a public benefit purpose in the legislation;
- strengthening the legal protection of the donee;
- ensuring a balance between freedom of contract and a social purpose;
- developing control and accountability mechanisms.

Through a scientific, theoretical and civil legal analysis of donation, we will identify the important conditions of contracts for providing charitable assistance to mahalla citizen assemblies.

Purpose and directions of charitable assistance: The contract must specify the specific purpose of charitable assistance, which must be of a generally beneficial nature, such as the socio-economic development of the mahalla, improving the living conditions of citizens, and developing social infrastructure. The goals of charity must be determined in accordance with the strategic development program and annual activity plans of the mahalla.

Subject of the contract (based on the requirements of Article 364 of the Civil Code) types and quantities of charitable property: The contract must specify in detail the specific type of property donated as a donation (cash, construction materials, machinery, equipment), quantity, quality, and technical characteristics. For monetary funds, the currency, amount, and payment procedure must be indicated, and for tangible property, the inventory number and technical passport data must be indicated.

Conditions determined as essential by law (pursuant to Article 511 of the Civil Code, purposes and restrictions for the use of charitable property: For donations made to citizens, use for the specified purposes may be indicated as a mandatory condition, and for legal entities, it may be indicated as a recommendation. The contract must clearly

indicate the permitted and prohibited directions for the use of charitable property, and restrictions on the sale, lease or pledge of property to third parties must be established. Conditions that must be agreed upon at the request of one of the parties (based on the requirement of Article 364 of the Civil Code): This category includes conditions that must be separately agreed upon by the parties based on the freedom of contract:

1. Delivery period and method

The donated property (money, things, equipment, food, clothing, etc.) must be specified with a specific date, time and method of delivery. For example, it can be clearly stated as "charitable property will be transferred to the building of the mahalla citizens' assembly by September 1, 2025." condition.

If the delivery of property is carried out in stages, the duration and volume of each stage should be agreed separately.

It should also be indicated which party will bear the costs of delivery (transportation, storage).

2. Terms of use:

Donated property should be used only for the specified public benefit (for example, developing the social infrastructure of the mahalla, creating a youth library, equipping a center for the disabled).

If the donor sets a specific direction, the mahalla undertakes to comply with this requirement. In case of violation of the terms of use, the donor may be granted the right to return the property or terminate the contract.

3. Control and reporting procedure

The mahalla citizens' assembly is obliged to keep separate records on the use of donated property and submit a report upon request of the donor or within the established deadlines.

Type of report: financial report, report on the work performed photo-video confirmations, cost estimates.

The donor may be granted the right to conduct control under the contract (for example, to check the intended use of property).

4. Grounds for cancellation

If the donated property is used contrary to the public benefit purpose established in the contract;

If the recipient (mahalla) fails to fulfill its reporting obligation;

If the property is spent for no purpose or directed to the benefit of another person is detected; in these cases, the donor has the right to cancel the contract and demand the return of the property.

In our opinion, based on the specific features of the donation and the organizational and legal status and activities of the mahalla citizens' assembly, we believe that some of the conditions analyzed above should be considered as important conditions. These conditions include the following

Financial control and accountability system: The mahalla citizens' assembly must maintain a separate register of the use of donated property, draw up periodic reports on the expenditure of donated funds, and should be made a condition for the donor to submit. The terms, form and requirements for submitting reports should be clearly defined.

Legal consequences of violating the terms of the donation: The contract should specify the donor's right to cancel the donation in cases of use of property contrary to the purposes of the donation, violation of reporting requirements. The procedure for compensating for damages caused by the violated terms and measures of liability should be clearly defined.

Procedure for changing the purposes of the donation: If the original purposes cannot be used due to changes in circumstances, the procedure for obtaining the donor's prior written consent to establish new purposes should be specified. If the legal entity providing the donation has been liquidated or the individual has died, the procedure for changing the purposes through a court should be determined.

The term of the charity contract: The contract should clearly specify the term of the contract, and the procedure for terminating the contractual relationship after the fulfillment of the charitable goals. For indefinite contracts, the grounds and procedure for terminating the contract should be clearly defined.

Rights and obligations of the parties: The donor's rights to monitor the proper use of the charitable property and to request additional information if necessary should be specified. The obligations of the local citizens' assembly to maintain the charitable property, use it properly, and report should be specified in detail.

Procedure for making amendments and additions: Amendments and additions to the contract should be made only by mutual agreement of the parties, in writing. The procedure for adjusting the terms of the contract in accordance with changes in the legislation should be specified.

It can be concluded that, based on the legal nature of the contract of donation made by individuals and legal entities to the mahalla citizens' assembly, its important conditions have conceptual significance in the following areas:

1. Subject (object) of the contract

The subject of the contract is the property or right donated as a donation. It must be clearly and clearly expressed: money, tangible items, construction materials, equipment and equipment, services or property rights. This condition is the main criterion for the validity of the contract.

2. Conditions determined as essential by law (based on Article 511 of the Civil Code)

Common-purpose purpose - the donation made in favor of the mahalla citizens' assembly must be in the direction of improving the living conditions of the population,

social infrastructure, education, culture or social protection.

Procedure for use - the property must be used for specific purposes and a special condition must be included in this regard.

Accountability - the mahalla must keep separate records and submit reports on the use of charitable property.

Change of purpose - property can be used for other purposes only with the consent of the donor or by court decision.

3. Conditions to be agreed upon by the parties (based on Article 364 of the Civil Code)

Delivery period and method - the date, method and by whom the property will be delivered must be specified in the contract.

Terms of use - donated property must be used only for socially significant purposes.

Control and reporting - the donor's right to control and request a report must be guaranteed.

Grounds for cancellation - the right to cancel the donation must be provided for in the event of misuse of the property or failure to provide a report.

4. Additional important conditions (based on the status and activities of the mahalla citizens' assembly)

Financial control and accountability system - determination of the form, term and procedure for reporting.

Consequences of violation of the conditions - compensation for damage, termination of the contract and liability measures.

The procedure for changing the purpose - with the consent of the donor or through the court.

Term – the term of the contract or the procedure for its termination after the purpose has been achieved.

Rights and obligations – the donor's rights of control, and the community's obligations of preservation and intended use.

Amendment procedure – amendments to the contract can only be made in writing and by mutual agreement.

The contract for charitable assistance to the mahalla citizens' assembly is a contract based on the principles of social justice, legal certainty and accountability, concluded in the interests of the population. Its concept is expressed as follows:

Purposefulness - charity must be carried out only for socially significant purposes.

Accountability and transparency - the mahalla must keep records of the use of charitable property and adhere to transparency.

Control and guarantee - ensuring the donor's right to control, requiring his consent or a court decision when changing the purpose.

Legal balance - ensuring a balance between the principle of freedom of contract and social goals.

Determining important conditions for contracts for the provision of charitable assistance

to the mahalla citizens' assembly by individuals and legal entities is necessary not only for legal reasons, but also to ensure social stability and the effective functioning of mahalla institutions. The concept of these contracts should be based on the principles of a common good, targeted use, accountability and legal balance.

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